

Combining future and past predictions of a linear Kalman filter for subviral particle tracking

Andreas Rausch^{1*}, and Thomas Schanze¹

¹ *Institute for Biomedical Engineering, University of Applied Sciences, Gießen, Germany*

* *Corresponding author, email: andreas.rausch@lse.thm.de*

Abstract: Automated tracking of subviral particles in fluorescence image sequences opens new opportunities for the research of medicines to fight Ebola and Marburg viruses. Based on tracking algorithms the motion and distribution of subviral particles in image sequences can be automatically analyzed. For this, an accurate tracking is mandatory. A method to generate a weighted mean of a two-sided Kalman filtering on interrupted tracks to recover lost data is presented. The method is extensively tested on one real track with a simulated interruption. The results show clear advantages of this novel adapted method over one-sided Kalman filtering and unweighted mean calculation.

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I. Introduction

The risk of pandemic spreads of severe viral infections shows the importance of a fast development of medicines. The Ebola virus which is a member of hemorrhagic fever pathogens has claimed more than 11.000 lives during the outbreak in West Africa in 2014 [1]. In cooperation between the Institute for Virology, Philipps-University, Marburg and the Institute for Biomedical Engineering, University of Applied Sciences, Gießen, an algorithm to automatically track subviral particle motion in fluorescence image sequences of infected live cells has been developed and presented [2]. The tracks serve as basis for further motion analyses of the subviral particles by various parameters. The tracking algorithm detects the subviral particles in all frames of a fluorescence microscopic image sequence. The tracks are stored in a list as coordinates for each moment of detection. Interruptions of the detection (caused by environmental disturbances and image noise) lead to the separation of one track into two individual tracklets. One track can eventually be fractionated into several tracklets under realistic circumstances. One track interrupted by a large gap into two tracklets is exemplarily shown in Figure 1a. To improve the tracking quality and reconnect track interruptions a linear assignment problem solver and a linear Kalman filter [3] are applied to the tracking data [4]. In this work a method to improve the Kalman predictions is presented. It is taken advantage of the fact that the tracking is not performed online by generating a forward and backward prediction of the tracking data. Using a novel weighting method, a mean prediction is created. The approach is described in the Methods section of this work.

II. Material and methods

The tracks and tracklets, detected by the tracking algorithm [2] and recombined with a combination of linear assignment problem solver and prediction of a linear Kalman filter [4] form the data basis for this work. Thus,

separated tracklets are already reassigned to each other but missing parts are not yet reconstructed by interpolation, as marked in Figure 1a (ellipsoid). The reconstruction of the lost data between the tracklets is performed using the same Kalman filter as for the reassignment. It is set up with a linear 2D motion model, predicting and correcting the particles' motion system state vector \mathbf{s} consisting of position and velocity using only position measurements. For each predicted/corrected state a covariance matrix \mathbf{P} is calculated, estimating the reliability of the state. It holds the variances σ of the positions x and y and speeds \dot{x} and \dot{y} :

$$\mathbf{P} = \text{diag}[\sigma_x \quad \sigma_y \quad \sigma_{\dot{x}} \quad \sigma_{\dot{y}}] \quad (1)$$

The longer the Kalman filter is predicting data without correcting them with measurements, the larger the entries of \mathbf{P} become. The Kalman filter iterates over the entire reassigned track calculating corrected states of the existing measurements and predicted states when measurements are missing (between assigned tracklets). The Kalman filter is processing the track data twice: into the future (forwards) and into the past (backwards) of a track. The processing is illustrated in Figure 1b. This leads to the presence of two Kalman filter predictions/corrections for each track position. Especially, in periods of missing position measurements of the tracking algorithm (gaps), the two predictions differ in their reliability affecting \mathbf{P} .

Figure 1: (a) A track is separated into two tracklets. The ellipsoid marks the gap where information is lost. The subviral particles movement direction is denoted by an arrow. (b) A linear Kalman filter processes the track twice: into the future (dashed line) and into the past (solid line). The processing directions are marked with arrows.

While the future prediction is more reliable in the beginning of a gap, the past prediction is becoming better towards the end of a gap. To profit from both predictions a weighted mean is calculated. Trust-coefficients for forward $\kappa_{f,t}$ and backward $\kappa_{b,t}$ prediction/correction at time t are introduced:

$$\kappa_{f,t} = \frac{\|\mathbf{P}_{b,t}\|_F}{\|\mathbf{P}_{f,t}\|_F + \|\mathbf{P}_{b,t}\|_F} \quad (2)$$

$$\kappa_{b,t} = \frac{\|\mathbf{P}_{f,t}\|_F}{\|\mathbf{P}_{f,t}\|_F + \|\mathbf{P}_{b,t}\|_F} \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbf{P}_{f,t}$ and $\mathbf{P}_{b,t}$, the covariance matrices of the track state at time t in forward and backward processing direction, respectively. F denotes the Frobenius norm. Note that the sum of $\kappa_{f,t}$ and $\kappa_{b,t}$ always is 1. The combined state $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_t$ is calculated from the trust-coefficients and the system states $\mathbf{s}_{f,t}$ and $\mathbf{s}_{b,t}$ of the forward and backward processing, respectively, at time t :

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_t = \kappa_{f,t} \cdot \mathbf{s}_{f,t} + \kappa_{b,t} \cdot \mathbf{s}_{b,t} \quad (4)$$

In practice, $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_t$ is calculated for each time of all tracks in a fluorescence microscopic image sequence. Here, the method is applied on one exemplary track, shown in Figure 1a. The track has been tracked with the actual tracing algorithm. Artificially, a gap has been placed in the track. Thus, the reconstruction of the presented method can be compared to the original track data. The mean distances between forward, backward, and combined states and the original track are determined for the interrupted part of the track to describe the quality of the track reconstruction.

III. Results and discussion

One real subviral particle track with an artificially created interruption is processed with the presented method. First the forward and backward predictions/corrections are calculated. The result is illustrated in Figure 2a. Based on the two directions of the Kalman filtering, the combined states $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_t$ are calculated. Figure 2b and c show the resulting

Figure 2: (a) The original, non-interrupted track (black line) is shown along with the future (dashed grey line) and the past (solid grey line) processing is shown. (b) The original, non-interrupted track (black line) is shown with the result track of combined states (grey line). (c and d) magnifications of the area, marked by a rectangle in (b), are shown. (c) shows the result of the weighted combined state method (solid grey line). (d) shows the result of simply forming the mean of backward and forward processing (solid grey line) Dashed lines show the distances between original (solid black line) and reconstructed track coordinates (solid grey line).

combined track. Additionally, the result of simply calculating the unweighted mean between the two Kalman filter directions is shown for comparison in Figure 2d. The mean and maximum distance and the standard deviation between forward, backward, weighted mean (novel approach), and unweighted mean and the original track within the interrupted part of the track (dashed lines in Figure 2c and d) are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: The mean and maximum distance and respective standard deviation between reconstructed and original track are listed. All distances are calculated for four cases: only forward Kalman filtering, only backward Kalman filtering, weighted mean of Kalman directions (presented approach), and unweighted mean.

Reconstr. style	Forward	Backward	Weighted	Un-weighted
mean	85.7 nm	59.7 nm	40.5 nm	41.4 nm
max	164.2 nm	116.8 nm	90.5 nm	87.2 nm
std	38.9 nm	24.4 nm	23.3 nm	28.3 nm

For comparison: the diameters of Ebola and Marburg viruses are about 70 nm [5]. Table 1 shows that the weighted mean and the unweighted mean between the two directions of the Kalman filtering lead to similar accuracies. With reference to Figure 2 it becomes clear that a weighted mean (b and c) is significantly closer to the original track than one sided Kalman filtering (a) and an unweighted mean (d). Note: the maximum deviation of 90.5 nm is not visible in Figure 2c, due to superimposition.

IV. Conclusions

A new method to automatically interpolate interrupted subviral particle tracks by an adaptive two-sided Kalman filtering is introduced. The weighting of the two Kalman predictions lead to a more realistic reconstruction of lost data. This forms an important basis for the high quality automated analysis of subviral particle motion. Image based research for antiviral agents can profit from the high accuracy of these automated tracking and evaluation methods. In future work the algorithm should be tested on and applied to more data.

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